

PHYSICAL SCIENCES

A DEEPER LOOK AT ELEMENTARY PARTICLES HAVING QUANTUM CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

In order to meet the desire of users to be constantly online, libraries, hospitals, hotels, airports, train stations, shopping malls, public places are installing more and more antennas emitting 2.45 GHz pulsed radiation, as well as in buses, subways and passenger trains. Wi-Fi consoles are used for gaming. Office and home appliances are also equipped with Wi-Fi antennas. Home routers often contain two Wi-Fi transmitters. As part of digital learning initiative, some European countries have decided to provide all schools with Wi-Fi networks. The vast body of research on health risks from Wi-Fi radiation is generally not addressed by politicians or public debate. The purpose of this article is to indicate how to avoid risks to human health under the circumstances. It should be noted that the electromagnetic fields themselves only heat the human body, and the torsion fields (longitudinal waves) that always accompany electromagnetic radiation act at the gene level. Exposure at the gene level is the main reason for the negative impact of electromagnetic fields on humans and animals.

Keywords: consciousness of elementary particles, torsion fields, interaction of torsion fields

Introduction

The Precautionary Principle (or Precautionary Approach) is a broad epistemological, philosophical and legal approach to innovations that can cause harm when there is a lack of extensive scientific knowledge on the subject. It emphasizes caution, pause, and analysis before jumping into new innovations that could prove disastrous. Wireless technologies are catastrophic.

The article describes the phenomena that cannot be described from the point of view of orthodox physics. It is assumed that the "fundamental" physical theory to be developed should be able to include the intelligent consciousness of elementary particles. This theory will allow us to reach a deeper level of description of physical phenomena. Prominent British physicist, Nobel Prize laureate Roger Penrose points out that this new, as yet absent theory, must be "uncomputable", that is, so that its action cannot be modeled by a Turing machine. The practical results described in the article may advance theoretical ideas for the creation of a new physical "fundamental" theory.

This theory will be based on internal simplicity and on the interaction of elementary particles with atomic nucleons.

It is known that atomic nucleons - protons and neutrons - are held together by a strong interaction. But the theory of the strong force was not developed to explain how nucleons stick together.

For years, physicists didn't understand how to use the strong force to understand the stickiness of protons and neutrons. One problem was the bizarre nature of the strong force—it gets stronger with distance, rather than slowly fading away. This feature prevented them from using their usual computational techniques.

It is believed that physical objects that are saturated with energies and represent ordinary matter are a particular form of matter infinitely refined and infinitely fast in its vibrations. It is able to penetrate any ordinary matter and create a source of movement

everywhere. It is located between the atoms of a crystal and the molecules of a living organism, and when it produces a local effect or when it is free, it is the same cosmic phenomenon or matter in motion, which we perceive as material energy and hardly imagine it as a specific form of matter in motion.

Oliphant, commenting on this view of energy, says: "It is nothing more and nothing less than what we habitually call 'spirit'. The mind is built into this unusual matter, as well as the will and any emotions. Jacob Boehme called it "celestial substance", and Swedenborg - "natural and spiritual atmospheres, composed of discrete particles of the smallest form." Prof. Crookes invented the word "protyle". Prof. Konas calls it "soul stuff" or biogen, while the Initiates call it "astral fluid". In fact, this is quantum consciousness.

But what is quantum consciousness? For example, Erwin Laszlo addressed this issue in his numerous publications, but this issue deserves a deeper consideration, including when probing elementary particles [1].

Common sense suggests that human consciousness is a stream of experience created by the brain. As long as the brain functions, there is consciousness; when the brain turns off, consciousness disappears. However, this is not necessarily the case. The brain picks up the signals, transforms them and reflects the result in the stream of our conscious experience. This is the essence of the standard scientific explanation of our perception of the world, but it is incomplete. It is incomplete not only because it cannot solve the age-old mystery of philosophers, how physical signals can be transformed into deeply felt conscious experience, and whether this transformation is the work of the brain, or whether the brain also transmits forms of consciousness from the surrounding world through virtual particles that also have consciousness, although far removed from the consciousness of people.

The development of quantum consciousness of

elementary particles can be the biggest step that will allow us to overcome the problems that threaten our life and future.

Scientists have not yet finally decided on the definition of virtual particles, and this concept has not received wide support among orthodox scientists. It is believed that it is an integral part of longitudinal waves, torsion fields, tachyon fields, etc. Most likely, these are the same particles isotropically filling space. This can be seen if you carefully read the characteristics of the mentioned fields.

Some evidence for the consciousness of virtual particles.

All objects in the quantum vacuum radiate static or they are otherwise called primary torsion fields, which weaken with distance. Secondary torsion fields are typical for dynamic systems and they are an open model of elements of the physical space structure [2].

Clearly, the quantum vacuum is not empty space; it is a significant element of the Universe. Just how significant we can only guess, but even a conservative guess would admit that it goes far beyond the significance attributed to the vacuum in the classical theories. These theories have already accepted that the behavior of elementary particles is influenced by the vacuum. Current research at the growing edge of science suggests that interactions between the vacuum and the observable world of macro-level objects are fundamental for our understanding of the nature of reality. Anatoly Akimov, G.I. Shipov and co-workers developed a sophisticated theory of the "physical vacuum"[3].

Having familiarized himself with the latest works on the theory of longitudinal waves, G.I. Shipov came to the conclusion that longitudinal waves can be characterized as torsion fields. Now it will be possible to work more fruitfully in these directions [4].

According to G.Shipov [1] it is postulated that the basis of all known quantum fields is a certain primary torsion field, which is a set of elementary space-time vortices that do not have energy, but carry information, i.e. torsion fields are transmitted informationally, not energetically. But at the same time, one very significant circumstance should be noted. An external torsion field of a physical object can change the internal spin structure (orientation of spins or rotation axes) without spending energy on it. Most likely, this is the result of the possession of virtual particles by their own consciousness. This is the essence of the informational nature of the torsion field. We will consider this issue later. But a change in the spin structure of an object, in turn, can lead to the fact that the physical characteristics that are associated with its energy change. This will be a secondary, but already energetic consequence. These are the experimental results obtained on a strictly physical level. Elementary particles, as mentioned earlier, have consciousness. Particle behaviour is purposeful, particles exchange information during an interaction. They must have a correlated view of space and time. We can say that the civilisation of particles goes a long way of its development. Two or more

particles can share a common strategy while being entangled. Confused, they nevertheless always act in concert. How can you test the proposed hypothesis? There can be at least two possibilities here. The first is to determine, for example, in an apartment the left and right torsion nodes of the Earth's geopathic zones (grid lines- GL).These lines are approximately parallel

to the lines of latitude and longitude and remain stationary for at least several years.

These lines are not detectable by magnetic field measuring instruments of high sensitivity, by electric field meters, or by air ion meters.

It is known that these sites contain virtual electrons and positrons [5,6]. By connecting the left and right nodes of the GL with a wire or a simple rope, we establish the state of harmonisation of the space in this room. This means that packets of ring waves from an electron and a positron are embedded in each other, and a true harmonisation of such an electron-positron vacuum occurs, while there will be no effect of the GL on human health. The second possibility consists in influencing the particles of these GL nodes with information. If you place a photograph of it on any of the GLs, then the state of harmonisation will also be established in the room, i.e. there will be no impact of the GL on human health. We emphasise that the setting up of such "information" experiments with virtual particles differs from everything that has been done so far in physics.

It was shown [5,6] that the carriers of torsion fields are virtual electrons and positrons. Nobel laureate Roger Penrose was one of the first to propose moving beyond neuroscience. Physicist Roger Penrose expounded a more radical point of view in the book [8] and later books [7]. R. Penrose was convinced that the "fundamental" physical theory, claiming to be complete at higher levels of physical phenomena, should have the ability to include intelligent consciousness [7].

Undoubtedly, the unity of the world is informational in nature. The formulated concepts should be considered only as a formulation of a problem that requires in-depth study, especially if we take into account the well-known limitations of models for describing torsion interactions. The consciousness of elementary particles plays a decisive role in physical processes. This tradition, which has long roots, allows us to naturally explain the seeming nonlocality and other paradoxes of the quantum world should mention that the Ukraine physicists noticed more than a decade ago that spin perturbations in spin medium are propagating in such a way that they cannot be screened, which in those times had no relation to the torsion fields. It means that there is a possibility of underwater and underground telecommunications, as well as communications through any other natural medium.

The coil, wound with wire or fiber, generates an alternating torsion field during the day, and in the vertical position the field is absent. If at one end of the coil standing vertically, put a magnet with the north magnetic pole, which generates the right torsion during the day, the oscillations begin with the right torsion field, ie virtual particles understand from which half-wave to start generation. If you put the south magnetic

pole, the generation will start from the left torsion field. This fact is another proof of the specific consciousness of virtual particles.

Once again, we note that for all the external heterogeneity of the examples considered, they have something in common. As already noted, in all cases, objects in observed processes and experiments or in natural phenomena have spin, meaning the classical spin, or angular momentum of rotation.

If the coil is unwound, i.e. straighten the wire, the oscillations disappear, since there is no interaction of virtual particles that were between the turns of the wire in the coil. The virtual electrons of a straightened wire, repelled by real electrons, are located at some distance from the surface of the conductor and interact weakly with each other. It must be remembered that in a coil of copper wire, located horizontally, virtual electrons will interact during the day, and virtual electrons at night. Another important concept in the theory of torsion fields is entanglement. When virtual electrons or positrons are entangled, the state of one becomes bound or correlates with the state of the other, regardless of the distance between them.

Although today there is no convincing evidence that the world has its own consciousness, but we will show with real examples that every particle in the universe has consciousness: our world owns consciousness, everything around us has consciousness. Traditionally, consciousness was considered within the framework of neurobiology, and after that a moral question may arise before us, since people look at objects with consciousness differently than at "non-living" ones.

Examples of torsion interaction.

We will give examples that, when analyzed together, will allow us with sufficient reason to assume the presence of specific interactions and fields generated by classical spins or angular momenta of rotations. Their properties, as follows from the above examples, indicate that if these fields exist, then they should be as universal as electromagnetic and gravitational, manifesting themselves at the micro- and macroscopic level.

For example, if we have a material object, a cone or a pyramid - no matter what it consists of - metal, paper, wax, hollow or cast, etc., we fix the right torsion field above the cone, and below it - below the base - left torsion field. Today this property of the conical object is already used in practice.

Consider the process of formation of torsion fields in a cone. The law of interaction of torsion fields consisting of virtual electrons and positrons is known: like attracts like.

Any material object has its own torsion field, consisting of virtual electrons, since virtual electrons are repelled by real electrons located in any material object [6]. The number of virtual electrons at the base of the pyramid is much greater than the number at the top of the pyramid, and some of the virtual electrons at the top of the pyramid are attracted by virtual electrons at the base of the pyramid, as a result of which a right field is formed above the top of the pyramid. virtual positrons, and at the base of the pyramid there is a left

field, which extends to 2/3 of the height of the pyramid, then there is a right field. This is the reality confirmed by measurements with a VEGA-12 [6] torsion detector and biolocation methods.

The above phenomena are referred to as the "shape effect".

Electromagnetic-free torsion field generators:

Simplest generators of torsion fields (L-C circuit) was consider in [6]. L-C circuit, also called a resonant circuit, or tuned circuit, is an electric circuit consisting of an inductor, represented by the letter L, and a capacitor, represented by the letter C, connected together. It means that the L-C system demonstrates spatial - temporal self-organization - the transition from the state of generation of the left TF to the state of generation of the right TF. The surprise is that harmonic oscillations are amplified in amplitude if the coil leads are short-circuited. There are some features in the work of such a coil.

If the spool stand upright, the oscillations disappear. But if a standing vertically to bring the magnet coil, the oscillations are renewed, while the horizontal arrangement of the coils in the presence of vibrations cease magnet near it. The explanation for these phenomena is given above when describing the operation of an aluminum disc [6].

Harmonization of the Physical Vacuum by other methods

These and other phenomena require careful study to understand the nature of the interaction of torsion fields in nature. This happens, in our opinion, because elementary particles have consciousness. Particle behavior is purposeful, particles exchange information during interaction. They have correlated idea of space and time and is easy to enter the synchronous generating mode. Our results motivate the widespread use of torsion field generation methods in future research and development of torsion communication.

We list some of them: the harmonization of the Physical Vacuum (PV) using a mechanical connection of conductive or non-conductive material regions with virtual electrons and virtual positrons, for example, "minus" and "plus" nodes of the Earth, a similar result reveals the connection of the poles of the magnet, and it is typical that in the daytime, the north magnetic pole has a right torsion field, and at night it has a left one. Magnesium, unlike other proven metals, has a right torsion field during the day. If we put a magnesium plate on the end of a vertically standing tube of small diameter, which generates a left torsion field from the end in the afternoon, then the PV harmony mode is established in an enclosed space. At night, everything will be the other way around, but the state of harmonization of the Physical vacuum is maintained. Similar phenomena are observed in wildlife: a cactus generates a right torsion field during the day, and a left one at night, similar to a magnet. There are many such examples. At the verbal level, the harmonization of PV is realized by singing mantras, for example, the OUM mantra, or by playing only one "C" note. PV can be harmonized with the help of the sound of Tibetan and Indian bowls.

The essence of Keeley's theory is based on the idea that the external musical tones of sound resonate with vibrations - the responses of the atom of the working fluid through the ether. All the listed phenomena of harmonization, except harmonization at the verbal level, are related to the so-called "entangled state", i.e. in this case, we carry out mechanical "entanglement" by connecting elements with opposite signs with a simple rope or conductive material. An interesting entanglement phenomenon can be accomplished with the help of a photograph of a geopathic zone node. When photographing any objects with modern cameras, the torsion fields of the complex material medium entering the input of devices with charge coupling together with the electromagnetic (light) flux change the orientation of the spins of the atoms of the recorded information in such a way that the spins of the recorded information repeat the spatial structure of this external torsion field. As a result, in any photograph stored in the range of devices with charge always, in addition to the visible image, there is always an invisible torsion image. If the printed photograph of the node of the geopathic zone of a certain room is put on the geopathic zone, then the space harmonization mode is set in this room. This action is similar to the harmonization of the Physical Vacuum in a confined space by combining the "minus" and "plus" nodes of the geopathic zones of the Earth. R. Openheimer wrote: "We do not understand the nature of matter, the laws that govern it, and the language in which it should be described."

PV can be harmonized on a verbal level by singing the OUM mantra or songs with a large number of "SI" notes.

Placing a geopathic photograph in some room on this same geopathic zone leads to harmonization of the PV of the premise.

The negative influence of the torsion fields of the base station of mobile phones can be eliminated by placing an artificial structure near the station with pre-recorded left and right fields connected together.

It is possible to eliminate the negative influence of the torsion fields of the base station of mobile phones remotely by placing an artificial structure on the photograph of the base station. This could be a device like "Vernada-Odo". It is well known that the Base Station and its photograph are in a confused state and placing on the photograph of the base station an artificial structure consisting of a pre-recorded left and right field on the corresponding host, connected together, ensures the elimination of the negative impact of the station on the environment.

Findings

A large number of options for harmonizing the PV are experimentally confirmed, which guarantee the minimizing the impact of electronic equipment on the living beings. By the harmonization of PV, we understand the elimination of the negative impact on human beings of all electronic equipment, including the influence of geopathic zones of the Earth. Torsion field studies have focused entirely on its effects on the health of living organism – the only results that truly

matter. It has shown profound beneficial results in human live blood cell and urine analysis, and significant improvement in health markers and behavior of animals (pigs, cows and chickens) [6,10,11].

PV harmonization can be carried out both due to the mechanical connection of spatial nodes with opposite signs of the torsion field with conductive and non-conductive material. The simplest confirmation of this thesis is the effect of combining the left and right nodes of the geopathic zones of the Earth, while there is no negative impact of the Earth's torsion fields on living beings.

PV can be harmonized by highlighting the enclosed space in blue.

PV can be harmonized on a verbal level by singing the OUM mantra or songs with a large number of "SI" notes.

When placing an artificial structure into a confined space with a pre-recorded left and right field connected together, the PV of this room is harmonized.

Placing a geopathic photograph in some room on this same geopathic zone leads to harmonization of the PV of the premise.

A similar result is obtained by connecting the poles of the magnet with any material, and it is characteristic that the north magnetic pole has the right torsion field in the daytime and the left in the night. At night, everything will be the other way around, but the state of harmonization of the Physical Vacuum is maintained.

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Many other options for eliminating the negative effects of electronics on living beings will be presented in future publications.

There are other techniques that allow you to harmonize PV.

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